

D3.2 – Functional samples description and test results

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Abstract

The deliverable describes BIMprove system's functional samples and its tests results. Results reported here represent the end of the first cycle, on which the basic functionality of the overall system can be demonstrated and initial knowledge about the system characteristics can be shown.

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Integration requirements, User tests, Validation

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AR	Augmented Reality
HMD	Head Mounted Display
MUVR	Multi User Virtual Reality
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (here: drone)
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle (here: also called <i>ground robots</i>)
CS	Coordinate System
TP	Test Person
VR	Virtual Reality
PC	Point Cloud
UI	User Interface
API	Application Protocol Interface
CAD	Computer Aided Design
BCF	BIM Collaboration Format

BIMprove project

In the past 20 years, productivity in the European construction industry has increased by 1% annually only, which is at the lower end compared to other industrial sectors. Consequently, the sector has to step up its digitization efforts significantly, on the one hand to increase its competitiveness and on the other hand to get rid of its image as dirty, dangerous and physical demanding working environment. Construction industry clearly needs to progress beyond Building Information Modelling when it comes to digitizing their processes in such a way that all stakeholders involved in the construction process can be involved.

The true potential of comprehensive digitization in construction can only be exploited if the current status of the construction work is digitally integrated in a common workflow. A Digital Twin provides construction companies with real-time data on the development of their assets, devices and products during creation and also enables predictions on workforce, material and costs.

BIMprove facilitates such a comprehensive end-to-end digital thread using autonomous tracking systems to continuously identify deviations and update the Digital Twin accordingly. In addition, locations of construction site personnel are tracked anonymously, so that **BIMprove** system services are able to optimize the allocation of resources, the flow of people and the safety of the employees. Information will be easily accessible for all user groups by providing personalized interfaces, such as wearable devices for alerts or VR visualizations for site managers. **BIMprove** is a cloud-based service-oriented system that has a multi-layered structure and enables extensions to be added at any time.

The main goals of **BIMprove** are a significant reduction in costs, better use of resources and fewer accidents on construction sites. By providing a complete digital workflow, BIMprove will help to sustainably improve the productivity and image of the European construction industry.

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1. Samples from Task 2.1 (Ground Robots)

1.1. Localization based on Marker data

Table 1 test setup for localization based on marker data

Input	Processing	Output
Marker → PTZ Cam → Init localization node	Package to map visual markers and use them to initialize the robot position with amcl localization(amcl_pose).	Ground Robot initial localization.
Main connection: Ground Robot Localization Involved: Robotnik		

Test Results

The robot can initialize the localization using the camera and markers.

See also: D2.1 Development of stationery, ground and UAV based data acquisition systems

1.2. Navigation of Ground Robots based on BIM data

Table 2 test setup for navigation of ground robots based on BIM data

Input	Processing	Output
SVG 2D Map	Getting an updated 2D map from the ground robot environment, and load to the map_server node for the robot location and navigation.	2D map Data
HMI/UI → Backend →	Base station	Waypoint description (xyz,psi), transfer to ground robot
Main connection: Backend Involved: Catenda, Robotnik		

Test Results

We have developed an automatic converter SVG to PNG map_server as an integration with Bimsync data platform.

1.3. Human Machine Interface (HMI) Ground Robots control and data acquisition

Table 3 test setup for human machine interface for ground robots control and data acquisition

Input	Processing	Output
Robot → Backend → HMI	HMI visualization interface for Ground Robot data.	Robots Sensors Data
HMI → Backend → Robot	HMI control and teleoperation interface for Ground Robots.	Teleoperation using web app and controllers.
Main connection: HMI Involved: Robotnik		

Test Results

Our HMI web application is working and able to teleoperate and visualize real time data from ground robots.

2. Samples from Task 2.2 (Drones)

Within the development of UAV based data acquisition systems 3 main samples are described here, each of them consist of "subsamples", that focus on more specific challenges.

2.1. Navigation of drones based on BIM data

Table 4 test setup for navigation of drones based on BIM data

Input	Processing	Output
Graphical user-input to generate a global path/waypoints for the scanning mission of the drone	Creating feasible paths based on the user-input. Waypoints in the correct coordinate frame, also flight velocities, UAV-orientation, camera triggers and camera angles are calculated	Waypoint Data (file or data struct)
Backend/User (.svg)	Base station	Waypoint description (xyz,psi) camera trigger etc., transfer to drone
Main connection: Backend		

Test Results

A simple functionality has been developed which is currently used in form of a script but can easily be integrated into a GUI for better usability. An open point is still the definition of the coordinate systems.

2.2. Data acquisition with UAV

Table 5 test setup for data acquisition with UAV

Input	Processing	Output
Waypoint Data	Flight with some interaction with an operator (e.g. a start permission)	Photos stored on on-board SD-card
Base-station	The drone	Images, flight data (x,y,z-positions, some log-data if needed)
Main connection: UAV – Base-station, real-time-visualization of drone		

Test Results

Currently the drones are able to follow the pre-defined waypoints and react to obstacles. One typical scan type is "scan along walls" in different heights. These scans are performed on waypoints-base but can be corrected by the on-board depth-camera (RS D435) i.e. "scan along the specific wall at a distance of 0.8 m", see also demos here: Development of stationery, ground and UAV based data acquisition systems

Coordinate systems (CS): The definition of reasonable coordinate systems are still an open point. At present the UAV starts at a specific location, that does not match the BIM - CS.

2.3. Processing of images to point clouds

The photos stored on the SD-card are transferred to a photogrammetry software (semi)automatically. There a data analysis/generation of point-clouds process is started

Table 6 test setup for processing of images to point clouds

Input	Processing	Output
Photos from Demo 2.2, Tag Coordinates	Tag information preparation	Tag-predefined PIX4D file
Photos from Demo 2.2, Tag-predefined PIX4D file	Few manual checks of the data needed, start photo collection generation	PC on local computer

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Drone	photo collection to PC	PC
Main connection: Drone-Base-station-PC, backend		

Test Results

Generally the quality of the generated point clouds are strongly dependent on the quality of the underlying image data and object surface appearance. Currently we still see limitation when light conditions are poor with homogenous shiny surface object in the test room; however, the result from a real construction site turns out to be very good even with low light condition. Therefore we follow two different paths:

- improving light conditions with artificial lighting, improving photos, photo collection based on photogrammetry
- photo collection generation based on the data from the depth camera we used for drone navigation (D435). Currently a test with a Lidar based Camera are running (RS L515).

2.4. User Interaction and Automation of Processes

Currently some manual actions are required in the overall process “BIM-data -> Point Clouds”.

Table 7 overview of user interactions and potential to for automation

What	User Interaction	Potential for Automation
1. BIM data to occupancy grid and path	run script, copy data	++
2. prepare drone for mission (charging etc.)	manual work,	++
3. Photo transfer	Connect work station to the camera	++
	Run transfer app	++
	Photo completeness check	o
4. Tag info. Preparation	Apply tag on constr. site	--
	Create tag info	--

What	User Interaction	Potential for Automation
	Create tag file Pix4D-mapper	o
5	Photogrammetry	Running PIX4D in command line Point cloud cleaning and cropping Exporting photo collection to Backend
		o -- ++

3. Samples from Task 2.3 (Safety)

3.1. Detection of safety structures and untidy places in images

Table 8 test setup for detection of safety structures and untidy places in images

Input	Processing	Output
Images of construction site stored in server	Searching safety barriers, safety nets, and untidy places from images. Stores results in a risk database.	Safety barriers, safety nets and untidy places annotated in the images. Results of the detection service stored in the database that can be queried through a specific API developed for risk data retrieval.
Main connection: Image storage, image analysis results Involved: VTT		

Test Results

From the received construction site images the vision based analysis will find objects of interest, safety barriers, nets and untidyness with adequate precision. The results of the image analysis can be accessed either programmatically or via a simple HTML based web user interface.

4. Samples from Task 2.4 (User Interfaces)

As described in D1.3 Concept descriptions of User Interfaces are categorised into the following six contexts of use:

- BIM@Construction,
- BIM@SiteOffice,
- BIM@OffSiteOffice,
- BIM@Emergency,
- BIM@Vehicle, and
- BIM@Anywhere.

As they are considered the two most demanding and most important ones, the first two categories of the above list have been not only conceptualised in detail in D1.3, but implemented as the first functional samples. This section of the deliverable reports about the functionality of these samples. Implementation of UIs will be described in further detail in D2.6.

4.1. BIM@SiteOffice: Multi-User-HMD-VR

The Vision for what a construction Site Office might look like regarding UIs has been described in D1.3 and is symbolized by Fig. 1.

Figure 1 BIM@SiteOffice visualization

The first functional sample being developed, is a Multi-User-Virtual-Reality-system (MUVR). This system can be used in a co-located setting (to be situated at the Site Office, for example), but the VR-session can also be joined remotely via network.

The functionalities of this first functional sample of the MUVR-system are also reported on in public deliverable D2.8 Layer Services. They are:

Navigation: The users can travel ("fly") through the model using their controllers and a point-and-fly interaction technique with a rubberband-physics-metaphor.

(De-)selection of models: Depending on how the model is subdivided, e.g. into discipline-models or by storeys, the users can hide and unhide these sub-models to inspect different aspects, using the hand-UI and the controllers.

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Communication: The users can see each other's avatars (you can also see, when an avatar is talking), hear each other via voice chat and use a virtual laser pointer to show each other things in the model.

Issue management: The system also contains the first version of functionalities for issue creation and management: With their controllers and the hand-UI, users are able to create and position question marks in the model that represent issues -- these (and most likely other symbols, depending on the nature of the issue) will, in the future, be connected to BCFs. Currently, an issue can be created, given 3D-coordinates by positioning the question mark, edited via menu, and deleted again. The functionalities related to issue management will surely be revised, amended, and be subject to user tests many times throughout the project, as they are among the most important features of this user interface.

Communication about issues: Since a likely use case for Multi-User-VR will be, to, as a group, go through the list of issues one by one to discuss them, there is also the functionality to

- click on an issue in the list to jump (navigate) to it directly, and
- summon everyone in the session to an issue in the list, to discuss this certain issue (this functionality is new and has not yet been user-tested)

Table 9 test setup for multi-user-virtual-reality-system

Input	Processing	Output	Comment
BIM (IFC)	Conversion: BIM (IFC) → Collada (DAE) → Unity StreamingAssets	Visualization in VR	This conversion is described in further detail in the public deliverable D2.8 Layer Services . It is carried out by the XR-viewer, currently, as it is still a standalone application. When interfacing the XR-viewer with the BIMprove-Backend, this conversion could be part of the processing handled by the Backend itself.
Point cloud (PLY)	Conversion: PC (PLY) → Unity StreamingAssets	Visualization in VR	see above
Issues (BCF)		Visualization in VR	

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BIM (IFC), PC (PLY), Issues (BCF)	Human inspection	Issues (BCF)	The XR-viewer is a User Interface. So the major part of the "processing" is human feedback to what is visualised through the interface. Much of this human feedback will be "channelled" and organised via BCF-issues.
Main connection: Backend Involved: FhG-IAO, USTUTT			

4.1.1. First User Tests

The first set of functional and usability tests was carried out in June 2021 (M10), and the MUVR-system has since been updated according to the test results. These were summative tests of the overall usability of the interaction techniques and the communication in the multi-user-setting.

The testing procedure is described in the table below:

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Table 10 testing procedure for MUVR

Phase	Item description	Goal / Research question	Method
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to test, test goals, and procedure. • Quick overview of used hard- and software 		
Technology-Introduction		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • give TP a rough understanding of functionality • get TP comfortable with hardware • adjust hardware to TP 	
<u>TP in VR (single user)</u>			
0) VR-Intro	explain VR devices and application	get TP familiar with VR devices and application	
1) Warm-Up-Tasks (get to know the functions and the model (building))	1.1 navigate (travel) (mode: point-and-fly with "rubber-band-physics") 1.2 use hand UI to 1.2.1 select/de-select (hide/unhide) discipline-models 1.2.2 scale the 3D-model (concrete m -> dm -> m) 1.2.3 create a (random) issue	usability of interaction techniques (how do TPs get on? Do they remember the techniques intuitively?)	think-aloud (qualitative)

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	<p>1.3 hide hand UI</p> <p>1.4 left hand laser point -> use grip in MU-mode</p>		
2) Test-Task: Specifically inspect one discipline model	<p>2.1 navigate to the labs in the building</p> <p>2.2 look specifically at the <electrics and lighting>/<HVAC (heating, ventilation, air conditioning)> model</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • usability of interaction techniques (how do TPs get on? Do they remember the techniques intuitively?) • which do they use when not explicitly told? 	think-aloud (qualitative)
Post-Questionnaire(s) part 1	Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motion sickness • test the questionnaire • later possibly find correlations to other findings 	questionnaire (quantitative)
	Igroup presence questionnaire (IPQ+)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • presence • test the questionnaire • later possibly find correlations to other findings 	questionnaire (quantitative)
Interview part 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any initial thoughts? • How was it? • Any feedback to the questionnaires? Or anything to add? 		guided interview, through MS Teams (recorded)

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did you get on with the user interface in general? • Did you like it? 		
break			
<u>TP in VR (two users)</u>			
3) Test-Tasks: Multi-User (TP A & B in VR)	<p>initially TPs A and B are in different locations in VR (only architecture- and lab-furniture-models are visible)</p> <p>3.1 meet in the labs 3.2 unhide HVAC and ELS 3.3 explain "your" models to each other 3.4 find problems, create at least one issue, and show to each other 3.5 find possible solutions</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • how are interaction techniques applied? • How do TPs communication • 3.1 how do they navigate? • 3.2 do the interaction techniques (menu) work? • ... 	observation (qual.)
break			
Post-Questionnaire(s) part 2	Game experience questionnaire (GEQ) (partly)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • group presence • test the questionnaire • later possibly find correlations to other findings 	questionnaire (quantitative)

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	System Usability Scale (SUS)	quick quantitative usability questionnaire	questionnaire (quantitative)
	Previous VR-experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • test the questionnaire • later possibly find correlations to other findings 	questionnaire (quantitative, qualitative)
Interview part 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any initial thoughts? • How was it? • Any feedback to the second round of questionnaires? Or anything to add? • How did you get on with the user interface this time around? • Did you remember the techniques from the first session? • How was the communication with your partner? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What went well / was easy? • What went wrong / was hard? • Any misunderstandings? • What did you like about the application and the whole experience? • What did you not like? What's missing? 		guided interview with two TP, through MS Teams (recorded)

4.1.2. Results and Consequences

The tests were carried out with two pairs of test persons: The first two are software engineers for VR software, the other two are researchers with a background in civil engineering. All of them are members of the Building Culture Innovation research team at Fraunhofer IAO.

The tests were carried out in German (briefings, communication in VR, interviews, and questionnaires) except for the first single session, which was done in English.

All test persons were pleased with the software overall. There is a slight learning curve and the interaction techniques do take a little getting used to. After learning them in their single session for the first time, the test persons asked for a short reminders of one or the other technique during the second (multi-user) session. A single reminder was usually enough, though. Nobody complained about any interaction techniques being unfit or counterintuitive for the tasks.

Some minor issues and bugs were found and reported during the tests and have since been tackled. Some additional functionalities were asked for, by the test persons, and have been implemented.

Changes are visible in the UI:

Fig. 2. on the left shows the hand-UI during the tests, the one on the right shows the revised UI.

Recognizable icons are now labelling the tabs at the top of the hand-UI and you can also tell, which one of them is currently selected.

The large BIMprove-logo took up too much space and its large transparent parts were confusing – it has since been reduced to a small logo on the top left.

Figure 2 hand-UI improvements

Issues are now shown in a list view (see Fig. 3.).

Each issue has a navigation-item to take the user directly to the position of the issue, and another one to summon all users in the virtual room at the position of the respective issue.

Figure 3 issue list

When inspecting "close quarters" of a building model with many people in VR, it can get crowded and avatars can block each others view. The latest version of the XR-viewer has the option of making all avatars transparent. The screenshot below also shows (from a PC-users point of view) the new part of the UI for this option and other communication options.

Figure 4 transparent avatars

4.1.3. Questionnaire Results

System Usability Scale (SUS)

The average SUS-score was 76.5, translates to high acceptability and adjective ratings between "good" and "excellent".

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The SUS is a tried and reliable method for a quick usability estimation. The achieved scores are good for early development.

Please note, that the SUS was taken after the first (single-user) session of the test.

Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ)

The Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) revealed no noticeable problems concerning cybersickness.

Igroup Presence Questionnaire (IPQ+)

The Igroup Presence Questionnaire (IPQ+) and Games Experience Questionnaire (GEQ) have not yet been fully analysed.

Questionnaires and other research results on usability, user experience, sickness and presence will be discussed in further detail in the updated version of deliverable "D1.3 User Interface concept" in M18 (Feb. 2022).

4.2. BIM@Construction: Tablet and AR-HMD

The first functional prototype of BIM@Construction has been introduced in D1.3. BIM@Construction has two versions, which supports following devices:

- Tablet
- Augmented reality head mounted display (AR-HMD)

Figure 5 Two versions of BIM@Construction: Tablet (left) and HoloLens 2 (Right)

4.2.1. First User Tests

The functional tests were done during user tests. There were four (4) test subject in the user test. System has two modes, the first and the third-person view. In the first-person view, the user experiences the building as if inside the building, either by using AR or in a tablet. In the third-person view, the user sees the building as an outside viewer. User had a scenario to execute which includes

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(1) system initialisation, (2) overview of general features, and (3) testing tools by doing scenario.

User devices were: Android tablet and Microsoft HoloLens 2

The testing procedure is described in the table below:

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Table 11 testing procedure for BIM@Construction

Phase	Item description	Goal / Research question	Method
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to test, test goals, and procedure. • Quick overview of two applications in Tablet and HoloLens 2 		through MS Teams (recorded)
<u>Tablet version</u>			
0) Handheld AR system -Intro	Explain AR tablet devices and application	get user familiar with AR devices and application	
1) Warm-Up-Tasks	System initialisation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initialisation of tablet with marker Overview of general features <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rotate-Zoom model • Change layers Hide/show • Opacity of structure and Floor 	usability of interaction techniques	think-aloud (qualitative)
2) Test-Task: Locate your self and check electrical wires with AR tablet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locate yourself by making the floor plan bigger • Jump in to Immersive mode • Check electrical wires on structure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • usability of interaction techniques • which do they use when not explicitly told? 	think-aloud (qualitative)
<u>HoloLens 2 version</u>			

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0) HoloLens system -Intro	Explain AR tablet devices and application	Get user familiar with AR devices and application	
1) Warm-Up-Tasks	<p>System initialisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initialisation of HoloLens 2 with marker <p>Over view of general features</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Show menu on palm • Rotate-Zoom model • Change layers Hide/show • Opacity of structure and Floor 	usability of interaction techniques	think-aloud (qualitative)
2) Test-Task: Locate your self, check electrical wires and use tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zoom in / out floor plan • UI & model to follow • Jump in to Immersive mode • Check electrical wires on structure • Measure location of the pipe • Add post-it note and put dimension there • Make warning sign 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • usability of interaction techniques • which do they use when not explicitly told? 	think-aloud (qualitative)
break			
Post-Questionnaire	System Usability Scale (SUS)	quick quantitative usability questionnaire	questionnaire (quantitative)
Interview part	For both devices, but focus in more advanced HoloLens 2 application		guided interview through MS

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Please use 2-3 words (adjectives) to describe your experience with the AR system. Choose the words based on your immediate impression.• Please explain why you chose these words / adjectives. <p>Dedicated question for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Menus and interaction• 3rd person mode• 1st person mode• floor plan / 2d map• Hololens 2 tools, like post-it note, measuring tool, signs <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Comfort of use <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Future improvements and missing features		Teams (recorded)
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4.2.2. Results and Conclusions

All users were able to execute all required evaluation steps with HoloLens 2 and tablet. All the functions and modes were working properly and gave feed to user via GUI without noticeable delay.

Overall, test users were satisfied or even impressed about the HoloLens 2 solution. However, those who were familiar with HoloLens 2 from other contexts had no difficulties in using the building model whereas those who were not, clearly had more difficulties and needed support in using the system. Users did not have difficulties in using the tablet version and there wasn't any need for support.

5. Samples from Task 2.3 (Backend / Main System)

The Backend/Main systems core role is to support the functionalities of the other parts of the system, and to make data generated there available directly and in processed form. This is done via APIs and web-based user interfaces. In a sense, the state of the backend "is" the digital twin (DT), but it should also support serializing the DT to open standard formats. This is explained further in Deliverable 2.8.

Currently tests are mainly performed on functionalities running directly on the backend and having no or only few connections to satellites. The following table describes the test on the scheduling:

5.1. Scheduling

Table 12 test setup for scheduling

Input	Processing	Output
Schedule in MS Project format and (future) IFC with 4D info	extract Tasks from schedule	Tasks stored in DB and showed in interactive Gantt chart
BIM models	extract BIM objects	Interactive 3D viewer showing model where objects can be selected
User input selecting a task and one or more IFC object	Create new link task-object(s) and store in DB	List of linked tasks and BIM-objects

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Figure 6 Gantt chart imported from a native MS Project file

Test results

Currently, the backend has an integration to the model server and the BCF server (both Bimsync). This enables support for IFC models and BCF issues. It has support for importing native Microsoft Project files (.mpp), and then this is stored as a schedule revision in a database and interactively visualized in a web interface as a Gantt chart. In the future IFC files with embedded task info (4D) will also be supported. Linking between tasks (lines in the Gantt chart) and BIM objects (selectable in the BIM viewer) is being developed. The web interface has a start page where one chooses which BIMprove project to work with, which leads to the main page for each project. The backend has support for parsing IFC-files, extracting this as meshes, and then comparing them with the Point cloud files and measuring signed differences as a basis for similarity comparison (as observed vs as planned). It also has support for comparing two IFC versions and creating a "difference model" showing what is deleted, added or changed. In the future it will support visualizing worker/drone positions in real time and in heat maps (over time), this is in development but not ready for testing at the time of writing. Via the BCF support (open standard for rich task system exchange), there is also a connection inside BIMprove, but also to other systems like the CAD tools (via plugins) and other well known domain tools like the Solibri model checker.

In summary, the backend has already some useful functionality, but all parts are in very heavy development. In addition, a lot of integration needs to be done. There still are several modules that will be added and those which are created still need improvement. This is in line with the project plan.